

Possible Exposure of Persons with Cardiac Pacemakers to Extremely Low Frequency (ELF) Electric and Magnetic Fields

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Abstract—The number of persons with implanted cardiac pacemakers (PM) has increased in Western countries. The aim of this paper is to investigate the possible situations where persons with a PM may be exposed to extremely low frequency (ELF) electric (EF) and magnetic fields (MF) that may disturb their PM. Based on our earlier studies, it is possible to find such high public exposure to EFs only in some places near 400 kV power lines, where an EF may disturb a PM in unipolar mode. Such EFs cannot be found near 110 kV power lines. Disturbing MFs can be found near welding machines. However, we do not have measurement data from welding. Based on literature and earlier studies at Tampere University of Technology, it is difficult to find public EF or MF exposure that is high enough to interfere with PMs.

Keywords—Cardiac Pacemaker, Electric Field, Magnetic Field.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN Western countries, persons with implanted cardiac pacemakers (PM) or implantable cardioverter defibrillators (ICDs) make up a large group. For example, in Finland, about 700 out of every million inhabitants received a PM in 2010. In addition, neurostimulators and drug pumps are quite popular nowadays.

A PM is a medical device with electrodes. The electrode configuration in PMs can be unipolar or bipolar. In the unipolar system, there is one electrode that lies within the heart as a cathode, where the anode is the metallic case of the PM itself. In the bipolar system, one lead has two electrodes very close within the heart [1].

In earlier studies [2]–[6], researchers found that some older PM models had shown to be susceptible to the electromagnetic fields (EMF) emitted by everyday household and workplace appliances.

In [7], investigators studied 11 volunteers with PMs and the possible interference when exposed to sine, pulse, ramp, and square waveform magnetic fields (varied up to 300 μ T) with frequencies of 2–200 Hz, generated using the Helmholtz coil.

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They also used an induction cooktop and a metal inert gas (MIG) welding machine to produce exposure. They found that three PMs with unipolar settings were affected by the highest fields of the Helmholtz coil and one of them also by the welding cable. They did not find any interference with any of the unipolar PMs when using the induction cooktop.

EMF interference with PMs and ICDs has been studied, for example, in Finland and France [8]–[10], [4], [11], [6]. The PM tests (in Finland) found that the electric field (EF) under a 400 kV power line (6.7–7.5 kV/m) may disturb a PM in unipolar mode, for example, during tasks under 400 kV power lines or at 110 kV (or higher) substations. However, the risk of interference is not considered to be high because only one of the several PMs tested showed a major disturbance [8]. For the 50 Hz magnetic field (MF), PM tests (in France) showed no interference under 50 μ T, in unipolar mode, or under 100 μ T, in bipolar mode [4]. For ICDs, in vitro tests (in France) showed no interference until 3,000 μ T, but only four devices were tested [11].

The European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) has also published some standards from this area [12], [13]. For example, according to the European Norm 50527-1, magnetic flux density (MFD) of 100 μ T is considered to be the ‘safety level’ for PMs. In addition, Finland has an act giving recommendations on the exposure of the general public to EMFs at the frequency range below 100 kHz [14]. The act is based on the European Council Recommendation 1999/519/EC.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the possible situations where persons with PMs may be exposed to extremely low frequency (ELF) electric (EFs) and MFs that may disturb the PM. The paper is based on our earlier articles [8], [10].

II. EXPOSURE TO ELECTRIC FIELDS

A. Examples of 400 kV Power Lines

At Tampere University of Technology (TUT), we have measured EFs and MFs in different situations, so we will use our old measurement data on public exposure situations.

In Finland, we have 400, 220 and 110 kV power transmission lines (frequency 50 Hz), and the total length of this transmission system is about 22,000 km. In the TUT studies of public exposure to electric fields near 400 kV power lines, the highest measured EF value was 9.3 kV/m.

In general, the values were lower [15]. Fig. 1 shows an example of a place under 400 kV power lines, where the EF is

6.7–7.5 kV/m [8].

Fig. 1 Example place under 400 kV power line

Fig. 2 Example of measurements in kitchen

Fig. 3 Example of measurements in kitchen

B. Examples of 110 kV Power Lines

In another study at TUT, the EF was measured at 10 tower spans near 110 kV transmission lines. The maximum

measured EF values were between 0.5–2.3 kV/m, and the mean value of maximum values \pm standard deviation (SD) was 0.98 ± 0.56 kV/m [16].

III. EXPOSURE TO MAGNETIC FIELDS

A. Examples of Power Lines and Cables

In a previous TUT investigation of 110 kV power lines, the maximum measured MFs were 0.6–6.0 μ T, and the mean value of maximum values \pm standard deviation (SD) was 2.98 ± 1.63 μ T [16]. Near 400 kV power lines (Fig. 1), the measured MF was 2.4–2.9 μ T [8].

Likewise, in another TUT study, MFs were measured near 110 kV underground power cables. Measurement places were chosen by calling different electric utilities and asking them about the currents in their 110 kV cables. Six cable routes from the service areas of two utilities were chosen, and measurements were made for both sides of the cable route. The maximum values were 1.7 μ T at the height of 1 m from the ground and 5.0 μ T at ground surface [16].

B. Examples in Homes

At TUT, [17] studied the MFs in rooms above indoor distribution substations, and the maximum values at the floor level were 0.37– 41.6 μ T. Moreover, we previously we measured magnetic fields in the kitchen. Figs. 2 and 3 show some examples [18].

Table I shows some examples of the MF measurements from different devices in a household kitchen.

TABLE I
 EXAMPLES OF MF MEASUREMENTS FROM DIFFERENT KITCHEN DEVICES

Kitchen Devices	MF (μ T)
Mixer with whisks	0.4–0.5
Mixer with whisks	0.8–0.9
Mixer with whisks	0.6–0.7
Mixer with dough hooks	0.9–1.1
Mixer with dough hooks	0.6
Mixer with dough hooks	0.5–0.6
Microwave oven 1	14
Microwave oven 2	6.7
Refrigerator 1	0.2
Refrigerator 2	0.3
Electric kettle	0.3–0.3

MFs were 0.4–1.1 μ T around the mixer and varied between 0.2 and 0.3 μ T around the remaining equipment. In the proximity of the microwave oven, the MFD was 6–14 μ T. The measurement distance was 20 cm, and in the measurements of the refrigerator, the height was 0.5 m. In the mixer measurements, three different power levels were also used [18].

C. Examples of Smart Meters

The use of smart meters has increased around the world. In Finland, these smart meters most often send information or communicate using either a radio frequency (800-3000 MHz) aerial signal to masts or a 50-100 kHz electromagnetic field signal through cables. TUT studied the possible magnetic field

exposures of the smart meters. TUT employed 46 smart meters that used Power Line Communication (PLC). The highest magnetic field was $0.48 \mu\text{T}$, which is 2% of the ICNIRP guidelines to public exposure [19]-[21].

Fig. 4 shows an example of the smart meter measurement with the MF meter MFM 3000—the separate probe version—by Combinova (frequency range 40–100 kHz and 10 nT-10 mT).

Fig. 4 An example of the smart meter measurement

The exposure of smart meters were so low, that there is not specific need to improve the sheltering of the meters from the public or to measure magnetic field emissions from all smart meters in the future. [21]

TUT also studied radiofrequency electromagnetic field exposure detected by smart meters during the remote reading of the smart meter. The measured values were less than 1-3% from the recommended values of ICNIRP. [22]

D. Examples of the Metro Station

TUT studied the exposure to ELF magnetic fields in the metro stations in Finland. The measurements concentrate on dynamic conditions. TUT measured magnetic fields in 20 cases when a train was leaving the platform in the same station. The magnetic field meter was MFM 3000. [23]

The maximum MF value measured was $5.4 \mu\text{T}$. The distance to the conductor rail was 4.3 m and the measurement height was 1 m. The MF only maintained this level momentarily, and the train influenced the general exposure

situation for about one minute as the train left. The fields measured were thus quite low when we compare them to the ICNIRP guidelines. The studied metro are powered by 750 V DC voltage supplied through a conductor rail next to the running rails, meaning. Therefore, it is possible that there are also DC magnetic fields near the metro as the train leaves the station. [23]

IV. COMPARISON EF EXPOSURE AND PM DISTURBANCES

As indicated above, the pacemaker tests found that the EF under a 400 kV power line ($6.7\text{--}7.5 \text{ kV/m}$) may disturb a PM in unipolar mode [8]. When we compare the EF exposures near 400 kV or 110 kV power lines to this study, we found that disruptive EFs are possible only in some places near 400 kV power lines. Such EFs are not possible under 110 kV power lines. When there is high voltage, then there is a high EF. Therefore, we know that in all other public places, EFs are lower than near 400 kV power lines. In addition, it is important to remember that we found disturbances only with a unipolar electrode configuration [8].

V. COMPARISON MF EXPOSURE AND PM DISTURBANCES

The MF is based on a current. In the places where we can find high currents, it is possible to find high MFs. Near power lines, MFs are not very high. Therefore, EFs are more important near 400 kV power lines.

As indicated above, pacemaker tests (in France) with MFs showed no interference under $50 \mu\text{T}$, in unipolar mode, or under $100 \mu\text{T}$, in bipolar mode [24]. It is possible that MFs of over $100 \mu\text{T}$ may be found near welding machines. Above indoor distribution substations, it is possible to find MFs that are high enough to cause disturbances, but in general, values are below $50 \mu\text{T}$.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on literature and earlier studies at Tampere University of Technology, it is generally difficult to find public exposure to EFs or MFs that are sufficient enough to interfere with pacemakers. Only the EF under a 400 kV power line may disturb a PM. However, in our earlier study, only one type, out of several tested PMs, showed a major disturbance, and that was only with a unipolar electrode configuration. The risk of disturbances is, therefore, not deemed to be high. Possibly near welding machines, the magnetic field can be so high that disturbances are possible, but as we do not have any measurements, we can only speculate.

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